

inDemand

Demand driven
eHealth co-creation

inDemand stories

DECEMBER 2020

The inDemand project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No763735

History

VS	Date	Changes made	Modified by
1	23.11.2020	First version	Elena López, Ticbiomed
2	12.01.2021	Addition of SENSE4HEALTH STORY Typo modified in RESOURCE PLANNING	Elena López, Ticbiomed

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inDemand Project Information

Title	inDemand - Demand driven co-creation for public entities
Duration	September, 2017 – November, 2020
Website	www.indemandhealth.eu/
Coordinator	Ticbiomed
Project overview	inDemand is a new co-creation model where Healthcare organizations (Challengers) and companies (Solvers) co-develop Digital Health solutions, with the economic support of public regional funds managed by Regional funding organisations (Funders). inDemand targets to solve Challenges identified by the Healthcare organizations.
Consortium	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1- TICBIOMED https://ticbiomed.org/en/ 2- SERVICIO MURCIANO DE SALUD https://www.murciasalud.es/principal.php# 3- INSTITUTO DE FOMENTO DE LA REGIÓN DE MURCIA https://www.institutofomentomurcia.es/ 4- RESEAU DES ACHETEURS HOSPITALIERS IDF - GIP RESAH http://www.resah.fr/ 5- CHOOSE PARIS REGION http://investparisregion.eu/ 6- MEDICEN PARIS REGION https://medicen.org/en/ 7- OULU UNIVERSITY HOSPITAL https://www.ppsHP.fi/Pages/default.aspx 8- COUNCIL OF OULU REGION https://www.pohjois-pohjanmaa.fi/frontpage 9- OULUN KAUPUNKI https://www.businessoulu.com/ 10- EUROPEAN REGIONS RESEARCH AND INNOVATION NETWORK ASBL https://errin.eu/ 11- UNIVERSITY OF OULU https://www.oulu.fi/university/

Glossary

inDemand methodology uses several words/names that have been created or adapted for the purpose of the project. These words/names have a precise meaning that is necessary to know to completely understand the process. Please find below the definition of these specific word/names

APPLICATION	Consist of the following items: 1/ The Proposal that must follow the templates provided for this purpose, 2/Declaration of honor duly signed stating that this very same project proposal does not receive funds elsewhere.
CALL	Publication of an announcement inviting a) Challengers to propose the needs in which the solutions will be based b) target companies to submit its proposal-application aimed to satisfy the identified challenges.
CHALLENGE	A Challenge is a precise unmet need identified by the challenger (more especially the Intrapreneur) that might be addressed by an innovative eHealth solution. To define a Challenge, an Intrapreneur has to complete the questionnaire dedicated to this and provide the following information: Definition of the Challenge, the Challenge scope (Scalability), the Functional requirements, the Expected impact, the Feasibility but also a Commitment to be involved in the inDemand project if the proposed Challenge is selected by the Evaluation Committee in phase 1. A Challenge is a Micro vision of the needs in the Healthcare organisation.
CHALLENGER	Public (healthcare organization), that identifies the unmet need through its professional, and frame it in the form of a challenge. They also work in close collaboration with the Solver to co-create a solution.
EVALUATION COMMITTEE OF CHALLENGES (ECC)	Group of people who are responsible for selecting the challenges that are winners among all proposals submitted by Intrapreneurs. The ECC must be composed of at least 6 people covering the following profiles: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Challenger (4 members): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Top management ○ Clinical ○ IT ○ Innovation • Funder (1 member) • Supporter (1 member)
EVALUATION PROCESS	The Call evaluation process is structured in three steps: 1- Eligibility Check. A first review performed by the Funder, 2- Proposal evaluation. A Selection Committee will evaluate all eligible proposals, 3- Solver selection. A list of beneficiary SMEs per Challenges will be published & notified.
EXECUTIVE TEAM (ET)	Manages and supports the process of challenge identification. This team is formed by technical staff, knowledgeable about innovation management and with access to the political decision makers. Typical candidates come from Innovation units of the public entity.
FUNDER	Organization that manages funding for innovation and is empowered to launch a competitive call to select the best Solver for each challenge. It also provides the economic support to the Solver to carry out the development of the solution.
INTRAPRENEUR	Professional person from challenger entity who proposes a concrete challenge and takes the commitment to develop by a pilot of co-creation in next phase if it is selected.
SOLVER	Private SME company that, once selected, becomes the solution provider, and starts co-creation with supporter and challenger.

SUBGRANT AGREEMENT	Selected Solvers are requested to sign a covenant document whose main objective is to validate financial and technical operational capacity from the SMEs teams, and to establish some minimum ground rules for receiving support from the inDemand project.
SUPPORTER	Intermediate organization that delivers support to optimize the business model, access to funding and commercialization of the Solver. It will also mobilize the local business ecosystem.
TOPIC	A topic is a large Healthcare area where there are needs that can be addressed by an innovative eHealth solution. The Topics are defined by the Top Management of the Challenger to focus the identification of challenges to most relevant healthcare areas. A Topic is a Macro vision of the needs in the healthcare organisation.
TOP MANAGEMENT	People who are decision makers in their entities, about policies and priorities.

Introduction

inDemand is a new co-creation model where Healthcare organizations (Challengers) and companies (Solvers) co-develop Digital Health solutions, with the economic support of public regional funds managed by Regional funding organisations (Funders). inDemand targets to solve Challenges identified by the Healthcare organizations.

The inDemand stories are a case study in .pdf format with qualitative and quantitative information that describes the original challenge encountered by the Challenger, the Solution co-created and the co-creation and business support participants that made it possible. Finally, it also includes testimonials from the participants.

InDemand Model

A3D → Non-invasive and easy to do undernourishment monitoring test for elderly people

The need

Development of a non-invasive undernourishment test and simple malnutrition monitoring for elderly people in institutions. Care homes for the dependent elderly are in most cases the last places where people live. It is therefore legitimate to consider palliative care in these facilities which is not only a legal obligation but is also a quality approach.

Impact

- Successful screening for 100% of undernourished patients.
- A personalized dietary care plan was provided for all of the undernourished patients and its results followed-up by a dedicated dietician.
- The screening process is faster and can now be performed without a physician's intervention.

[*] These results come from regular end-user testing during the project - 10 months

The solution

The solution implements a digital version of the Nutrition Focused Physical Examination (NFPE), which is one of the new methods for identifying undernutrition. For a maximal impact, this new screening and follow-up assessment methodology is integrated into a global service that provides remote support (teleconsultation) from registered dietitians to assist the healthcare organization in translating screening and patient data into effective nutritional care. This approach makes it possible to offer an alternative to the invasive use of blood tests to measure albumin and CRP while providing better prospects for the personalization of patient care.

#Nutrition

#DigitalHealth

#CareHomes

Co-creation and Business Support

Pilot region: Paris (France) | Period: August 2019 – August 2020

Challenger	Solver	Users	Supporter	Funder
EHPAD Louise Michel, GCSMS91	Winnov with its service CDIET	Health managers, coordinating nurse and assisting nurses	Medicen	Choose Paris Region
1 Nursing Homes Group Coordinator 1 Care Coordinator 2 Doctors 1 Nutrition Doctor 3 Nurses	1 R&D leader 1 medical advisor 1 product managers 1 project manager 2 full-stack developers	4 members of the care home staff and 54 patients used the solution during the co-creation process	2 business supporters	1 Project manager

Hear the stories!

CDIET provides a fast, simple and efficient answer for the screening and management of nutrition-related troubles, a key factor to maintain older adults' autonomy and well-being. Through the addition of the Nutrition Focused Physical Exam in the application, we were able to extend CDIET clinical scope to help us provide the patients with new improved, personalized therapeutic strategies.

Doctor Lawrence BORIES, Geriatrician in the CHI du Val d'Ariège, Head of the Mobile Geriatric Unit in Ariège, Head of the Silver Economy group for the WHO's APTITUDE project

inDemand enabled us to further develop our malnutrition screening and management service through the integration of image-based smart forms for a better and more accurate diagnosis. The involvement of clinicians and nursing home staff all along the co-creation process provided the tech/service design team with real-life feedback to ensure the newly developed tools were relevant with their work and organisation.

Luc Vialard, CEO at Winnov

About inDemand

inDemand boosts digital health solutions proposed and co-created with healthcare professionals

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ACRA → An effective algorithm that identifies patients susceptible to get complications that cause readmissions in Intensive Care Units

The need

Unscheduled re-entry of the patient in the ICU is an adverse event that causes an increase in morbidity, mortality and consumption of hospital resources. A recent meta-analysis has reported an average re-entry rate between 4 and 7%, although it can reach up to 14%. The average mortality of patients with unintended readmission in the 72 hours after discharge from the ICU is 33%.

The solution

The solution consists of a supervised learning model where each patient with unintended readmission in the 72 hours after discharge from the ICU are predicted as TRUE or FALSE. Additionally, reports with field importance are included (e.g. related complications, oxygen saturation level, text from the discharge summary, among others). The aim is to identify which factors have more influence in readmission helping ICU professionals to better understand what triggers readmission and enabling early detection of risk factors.

Impact

73.5% accuracy of the tool

ROC Area Under the Curve = 0.7602 in a fusion as a combination of nine ensembles (Higher AUC values indicate a better classifier performance)

#BigData

#PredictiveCare

#IntensiveCare

Co-creation and Business Support

Pilot region: Murcia (Spain) | Period: May-Dec 2018

Challenger	Solver	Users	Supporter	Funder
SMS	BigML	Healthcare Professionals	Ticbiomed	INFO
1 Intensive Care Professional	1 Lead Data Wrangle 1 Partner Development Manager	1 Intensive Care Professional 4 IT Personnel	2 business supporters	2 experts

Hear the stories!

I see a change of paradigm in terms of our healthcare practice. There are other types of procedures, technologies and methodologies to do things that are innovative and that aren't incompatible with our current practice

Juan Alfonso Soler, Intensive Care Professional at SMS

One of the advantages is to have a solution to solve professionals' real problems; defined by them and for them

Jaime Boscá, Partner Development Manager BigML

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ARNO & ANONYMOUS →

Non-opposition collection electronic system & Anonymization of patient data for research purpose

The need

In the era of big data and advances in data analysis, the collection and storage of this data for exploitation and possible publication seem essential to produce and develop scientific knowledge in research. However, there is always a risk of re-identification. Another problem typically faced to create a health data warehouse is to collect non-objection (paper form) on a massive scale and to ensure that the choice of patients to not be included in the database is respected.

Impact

- Patient satisfaction thanks to the information given about their data and an easy-to-use option
- 100% of healthcare professionals see Arno saving time on the management of patient oppositions
- Facilitate the exchange of data between healthcare professionals by guaranteeing patient safety

[*] These results come from regular end-user testing along the project - 12 months

The solution

ANONYMOUS and ARNO respectively ensure patient's rights to privacy, through anonymization of datasets, and rights to the opposition of data re-use all along with retrospective research protocol, such as clinical studies employing solely data already produced by medical practitioners. These products encompass for GDPR requirements around data processing of medical data in the context of retrospective research and make them user friendly for the various stakeholders, operationally efficient and more respectful of patient's rights. Once plugged to a medical data warehouse, such as Dr Warehouse, the time to conduct GDPR-compliant retrospective research goes down to days instead of months/years.

#MedicalDataPrivacy

#PatientsConsent

#DrWarehouse

Co-creation and Business Support

Pilot region: Paris (France) | Period: August 2019 – August 2020

| Funder |
|--|--|--|---|--|
| GHU Paris | Codoc | Several | Medicen | Choose Paris Region |
| 1 Project Director
1 Project Manager
1 Chief information security officer
1 Data Protection Officer | 1 R&D leader
1 Medical advisor
1 Back-end developer
1 Project manager | A total of 10 users from:
-The department of medical information
-Researchers
-Doctors
-Clinical Research Department | 2 business supporters | 1 Project manager |

Hear the stories!

With tools like Arno and Anonymous, it looks like we will finally have the perfect instruments to harness the vast amount of clinical data we have been collecting over the years, whether it's to quickly test new scientific hypotheses or to help us define new ones

Fabien Vinckier, Hospital practitioner and university lecturer in psychiatry

Thanks to this co-creation, we can propose tech solutions for one of the most challenging entry barriers of retrospective research on medical data: reglementary aspects (GDPR). Dr. Warehouse offers a solution for hospital efficient data exploitation, with Arno and Anonymous we are getting closer to our vision: an end-to-end platform to transform hospital data into medical discoveries and better care for the patients

Lucien Roquette, CTO at Codoc

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BUDDYCARE → Electronic guidance and advice pass (case: breastfeeding guidance)

The need

A breastfeeding pass is a tool used by a mother and child clinic and the hospital for implementing breastfeeding guidance and information transfer as a part of the job of caring for a newborn. It has been developed in cooperation with the city of Oulu to promote breastfeeding. For the time being, the card is printed on paper so health care personnel is unable to carry out the necessary real-time entries regarding the implementation of the guidance. Every family is entitled to sufficient breastfeeding guidance as this promotes establishing and sustaining exclusive breastfeeding in accordance with the national and international recommendations. Both the mother and her family benefit from access to proof-based information regarding breastfeeding.

Impact

- 100% would either highly or somewhat highly recommend the app to other pregnant women and mothers
- 75% said that by using the app, they increased their knowledge about breastfeeding
- 92% said the app was either very or somewhat easy to use and they preferred using it to a paper format of the breastfeeding guidance pass

(* These results come from regular end-user testing during the co-creation by healthcare professionals at the Oulu University Hospital Testbed.

The solution

The BuddyCare breastfeeding guidance app has several features which make it easy-to-use for families at the same time providing them with information in a simple format. Smart communication between the mobile app used by families and the dashboard used by care personnel allows two-way communication between the healthcare professionals and families. All important information during the pregnancy period and after giving birth is found in the app on a simple timeline, where it's easy for the family to go through the guide step-by-step. It is also possible for families to write notes about issues they would like to bring up during appointments at the child health centre. In the mobile app, families also find links to different official healthcare websites where they may read additional instructions.

#Breastfeeding

#Digitalguidance

#Digitalhealth

Co-creation and Business Support

Pilot region: Oulu (Finland) | Period: May 2018 - December 2018

| Funder |
|--|--|---|---|--|
| Oulu University Hospital | Buddy Healthcare | Pregnant women and their family members | BusinessOulu | Oulu Region Council |
| 4 Head Nurses
1 Quality Manager | 1 COO
1 UX/UI Designer
4 Software developers
1 QA Engineer | 13 pregnant mothers | 2 business development experts | 2 experts |

Hear the stories!

I am happy about the active collaboration between health care professionals and technology developers. We reached our goal to provide evidence-based breastfeeding guidance to mothers.

Pirkko Nikula, Head Nurse at Oulu University Hospital

InDemand process taught us efficient and goal-oriented development together with healthcare professionals

Peter Hänninen, COO, Co-founder, Buddy Healthcare

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DEEP DIVER → Assistance in the search for diagnoses with suspicion of Occupational Diseases

The need

Occupational Diseases (OD) are a group of pathologies whose causal relationship with the job is proven, and which implies a legal responsibility in their prevention and care. However, most OD go unnoticed as Common Diseases, with the public system assuming their costs. The Murcia Health Service has implemented a system of OD suspicion alerts on new diagnoses in the Primary Care (PC) application facilitating the telematic communication of the suspicion to the Health Inspection. However, alerts only act when a new episode is opened in PC, without acting on historical episodes where most chronic diseases and cancers are. The need is to extend the alerts to detect suspicions of OD by taking advantage of all the information in the clinical history of PC and hospital, as well as the free text of the clinical records.

Impact

- Area under the ROC curve = 0.983, just seventeen thousands from perfection (=1).
- 4.207 suspicions of Occupational diseases validated.
- Over 250,000 historical electronic medical records tracked.

The solution

A set of Natural Language Processing techniques and classification algorithms has been applied to electronic health records to develop a system that is able to detect the suspicion of occupational diseases. The system has managed to successfully analyze hundreds of thousands of electronic medical records and discover suspicions of occupational diseases related with asbestos that have been validated by a committee of medical experts in the field.

#DeepLearning

#NLP

#OccupationalDiseases

Co-creation and Business Support

Pilot region: Murcia (Spain) | Period: June 2019-September 2020

| Funder |
|--|--|---|---|--|
| SMS and Murcia Health Ministry | Vócali | Health inspectors | Ticbiomed | INFO |
| 1 innovation professional
3 IT professionals
1 clinic documents expert
2 health inspectors from the Health Ministry | 3 engineers | 2 health inspectors from the Health Ministry
1.300 potential end users among Primary Care physicians | 2 business supporters | 2 experts |

Hear the stories!

InDemand has been an opportunity to collaboratively develop a technological tool that speeds up the identification of patients treated by SMS with potential occupational diseases such as pathologies caused by asbestos. This makes significant progress for the Unit for Monitoring Suspicions of Occupational Diseases.

Miguel Soriano Contreras, Health Subinspector at the Health Ministry

Solver and Challenger, we spoke different languages. Ones about algorithms and the others about the clinical processes, but in the end, we managed to understand each other and to build a very comprehensive solution for the detection of occupational diseases.

Pedro Vivancos, CEO at Vócali

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Región de Murcia
Consejería de Salud

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DIGITAL ACTIVA → A tool to help the management and monitoring of physical exercise prescribed for health

The need

The prescription of physical exercise from primary care (PC) is considered a fundamental tool in the fight against sedentarism. However, it is still a challenge to manage this prescription in an individualized way, and also to be followed by the health professional. The Murcia-ACTIVA Program was implemented in the Region of Murcia in 2010. Three entities collaborate in this program: Murcia Health Service -Servicio Murciano de Salud (SMS)-, whose health workers prescribe physical exercise; Town Councils provide timetables and sports facilities and assign a technician to receive prescriptions via fax from the corresponding Health Centres; and graduates in Physical Activity and Sport Sciences, who are responsible for implementing the program and analyzing the evolution of each individual's physical condition. Although the Activa program has been a success, there are still areas for improvement: 1. Accessibility (only 66.5% of patients who receive a prescription for physical exercise do so in sports centres, mainly due to the paper-based and bureaucratic process) 2. Follow-up and adherence.

The solution

Application for prescribing physical exercise for health, follow up on real-time these prescriptions, establish a process and communication between medical staff and sport facilities, and implement adherence strategies for patients. There are different interfaces for GPs, trainers and patients. The application contains gamification to engage the users.

#ExercisePrescription

#Wellbeing

#Sports

Impact

- Average satisfaction rate was 7.3/10 among GPs, trainers and town councils

(*) These results come from a 2 months trial period

Co-creation and Business Support

Pilot region: Murcia (Spain) | Period: June 2019-September 2020

Challenger

Solver

Users

Supporter

Funder

SMS

Upicus

Activa Programme

Ticbiomed

INFO

1 innovation professional,
1 IT professional
From the Activa Programme:
1 head of programme,
1 nurse
3 GPs
1 trainer

3 software developers
2 quality assurance
1 UX designer
1 Chief Technical Officer
1 customer success marketing and sales

1 head of programme,
1 nurse
3 GPs
1 trainer

2 business supporters

2 experts

Hear the stories!

InDemand's co-creation process has allowed us to find easy solutions to hard problems.

InDemand allows the voice of patients to be heard in a co-creation process and ensures that the solutions are effective and efficient.

**Esther García, Trainer
M^ª Lourdes Fernández, Physician
M^ª Alegría Avilés, Nurse
Javier López Román, Physician
Members of Activa Programme**

Through the co-creation process, we are listening to the needs and experience of the users. Besides, we are opening the eyes of the challengers to what technology can do for them. The result is a very complete product, with lower risks and costs for both parts.

Juan Saussol, CEO at Upicus

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EPICO → Digital patient-doctor communication channel for epilepsy management

The need

Epilepsy affects 0.7 - 1% of the general population. At least half of the patients with epilepsy are young and active. These patients need regular follow-ups with hospital Neurology services or Epilepsy Units. The waiting list for appointments with the doctor has an average of 6-9 months. Consultations related to epilepsy account for 2% of total visits to the Emergency Department. Most of these consultations are due to the decompensation of known epileptic patients or precipitated seizures. On the other hand, neurologists have little time in consultation to train and inform patients and their families.

Impact

- ↑50%** • Patients satisfaction: ↑ 50% (before-after pilot).
- ↑2.5** • Quality of life: ↑ 2.5 points
- 3,72** • Average response rate of neurologist: 3,72 min

(*) These results come from a 2 months trial period

The solution

Epico is a communication platform for epileptic patients and their doctors. EPICO consists of an end-user app (EPICO App), a dashboard for the doctor for the management of patients (EPICO Doc) and EPICO Cloud for data communication with the systems of Servicio Murciano de Salud (SMS). EPICO App allows patients to log their seizures and to keep records of the seizure length, type, potential triggers, a description of associated symptoms and it also integrates with sleep xtracker bands. As a new event is recorded by EPICO App, a notification is sent to EPICO Doc, so that doctors are aware of the progress of the disorder and can prescript patients better treatment.

#PatientEmpowerment

#SelfManagement

#Telemedicine

Co-creation and Business Support

Pilot region: Murcia (Spain) | Period: May-Dec 2018

| Funder |
|--|--|---|---|--|
| SMS | Oxiframe | Epilepsy patient | Ticbiomed | INFO |
| 2 neurologists | 1 Product Manager
1 Front-end developer
2 Back-end developer | 25 male patients
29 female patients | 2 business supporters | 2 experts |

Hear the stories!

InDemand has allowed us to start from our needs, from what we live on a daily basis and how we work with patients. We see the flaws and improvements that could be applied.

**Irene Villegas,
Neurologist at SMS**

Thanks to co-creation, the app development has been fully guided by the users - both patients and doctors. This a winning approach.

**Raquel Yuste,
Front-end developer at Oxiframe**

My epilepsy is somewhat resistant to medication. I once had kidney problems and weight loss. It wasn't until a few months after that my neurologist discovered it was because of the medication. With EPICO those months of pain would have been shortened into days. I could have recorded those pains on the calendar and contacted my neurologist directly through the internal doctor-patient communication channel.

**Patient,
30 years old, male**

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ePREVENT → e-Consultations in the management of alcohol dependency

The need

Part of the French population is followed up for addictology/alcohol-dependency issues. A significant part of those patients is cured in Emergency Rooms. Yet, after this episode, most fail to integrate a tailored addictology monitoring process. Also, doctors lack information and tools to better monitor the patients between two consultations in order to prevent or better manage craving events. As more and more patients are followed by several doctors (psychiatrists, general practitioners etc.) the need to network increases.

The solution

Pulsio Santé is an e-health platform for e-consultations, accessible to alcohol-dependent patients monitored in the Liaison, Addiction Treatment Teams Unit and to their addictology specialist, compatible with the telemedicine charter validated by the Physicians' Order. Pulsio Santé allows patients to monitor their addiction risks and offers health professionals engaging tools to reach patients through teleconsultations and follow-up surveys. Health professionals use Pulsio Santé to collaborate thanks to communication tools and access to patients' medical records.

Impact

- Increase of 70% patient's satisfaction thanks to teleconsultations and at-home follow-up functionalities
- 100% of health professionals see Pulsio Santé a way to avoid foregoing medical treatment
- Improvement in appointment and consultation observance from patients

#DigitalHealth

#Teleconsultation

#AlcoholDependency

(*) These results come from a 3 months trial period

Co-creation and Business Support

Pilot region: Paris (France) | Period: September 2018 – March 2019

| Funder |
|---|--|---|---|--|
| Hôpital Foch & Resah | Pulsio Santé by Stimulab | Addictologists and patients with dependency issues | Medicen | Choose Paris Region |
| 1 project director
1 project manager
2 addictologists and psychotherapists
1 quality director
1 information systems director
1 nurse coordinator
2 nurses | 1 R&D leader
1 medical advisor
1 product manager
1 front-end developer
2 back-end developers | 106 in April 2020 in Hôpital Foch

Patients profiles: born between 1941 and 2001;
65% men - 35% women;
substances: alcohol, tobacco, cannabis, cocaine, codeine | 2 business supporters | 1 project manager |

Hear the stories!

ePrevent provides us with the tool to really use telemedicine to its full potential and has challenged ourselves to adapt our own ways of working. The co-creation process benefits us to have a tailored-made solution, that can yet be duplicated elsewhere, and we are starting to do so.

Dr Christine FAIVRE , Addictologist and Psychotherapist at Hôpital Foch

InDemand has allowed us to implement an innovative platform focused on addictology thanks to the participation of health professionals who were ready to share experiences and collaborate to reach clinical success

Marc-Antoine Brochard, Pulsio Santé CEO

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GRAVIDITY → Digital card for monitoring pregnancy and puerperium

The need

Three types of professionals from different fields are involved in the monitoring of normal pregnancy: Primary Care (PC) midwife, PC doctor and the hospital obstetrician-gynaecologist. To guarantee continuity of care in the monitoring of pregnancy, the Pregnancy Card was created in Murcia Health Service, a common register printed on paper that protects the pregnant woman and in which all the professionals involved register in hand-writing format. These records include filiation data, medical and obstetric history, analytical tests, ultrasounds, incidences, notes. However, this format has many limitations, such as its partial completion, problems of security and confidentiality of printed data, the lack of proactivity in the role of women, unnecessary waste of paper, confusions produced by the manual text and lack of coordination among professionals.

Impact

- High patient satisfaction. Net Promoter score = 7/10
- High Healthcare Professionals Satisfaction. Net Promoter score = 7/10
- Average logged in time of 20 min per week
- Challenger showed a willingness to gradually scale-up the solution

(* These results come from a 7 months trial period with 47 pregnant women and 33 healthcare professionals across three healthcare centers

#Pregnancy

#PROMs

#DigitalTools

The solution

GRAVIDITY is a cloud-based digital solution that supports healthcare teams in monitoring and following up on their pregnant patients and allowing women to empower the self-management of their pregnancy and puerperium up to 6 months.

Co-creation and Business Support

Pilot region: Murcia (Spain) | Period: June 2019-September 2020

| Funder |
|--|---|---|---|--|
| SMS | Promptly Health | Pregnant women and Healthcare Professionals | Ticbiomed | INFO |
| 1 innovation professional
1 GP
1 gynecologist
2 midwives
1 IT professional | 1 Head of Product
1 CEO
1 CTO
1 Project Manager
5 Software developers
1 UI/UX Designer | 47 pregnant women
33 healthcare professionals (midwives, doctors, gynaecologists) | 2 business supporters | 2 experts |

Hear the stories!

InDemand has allowed us to improve, with a digital solution, the accessibility and monitoring of pregnancy and puerperium up to 6 months for the pregnant woman, empowering her in the self-management of her process, as well as for the professionals involved in the care.

Fernando Araico, Gynecologist at SMS
Pablo Serrano, Midwife at SMS

Our participation in this InDemand project allowed us to develop a digital solution specifically focused on pregnancy and thus, to expand our product portfolio. Undoubtedly, the co-creation process with a motivated clinical team with expert knowledge on maternal care contributed massively to the success of the final digital solution

João Fidalgo, Project Manager at Promptly Health

Gravidity has provided me with the information and monitoring throughout pregnancy and the puerperium with great efficiency and safety, being of great help during the situation experienced by the pandemic of Covid-19

Beatriz, 33 years old
Pregnant women

About inDemand

inDemand boosts digital health solutions proposed and co-created with healthcare professionals

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The inDemand project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No763735.

HEAT → An online platform to help in the planning, monitoring and evaluation of specialized healthcare education delivered in hospitals

The need

The Specialized Healthcare Training programme in Servicio Murciano de Salud manages medical residents that pursue their medical specialization. They needed to improve the processes of information collection, evaluation and monitoring of the specialized health training that they were carrying out with office and paper-based solutions. In health training, different roles intervene and each one has obligations and responsibilities, so it was also necessary to improve the communication processes between them.

The solution

A specialized teaching solution developed to support the needs of the centre in the registration, monitoring and evaluating the activity of its Medical Residents, in standardized electronic forms and on a single online platform. The actors will not have to waste time and paper, chasing other actors that have to evaluate the rotations; the system will do it for them through a notification system. Moreover, with a single click, the tutors will submit annual reports without having to search for information.

Impact

- Improvement of communication between the actors
- More integrity and security of data
- Immediacy and availability of information easily and 24/7
- Savings of 54 printed sheet of paper per professional & year (→51,000 potential)

(*) These results come from a 2 months trial period

#Standardization

#CommunicationTools

#DigitalTransformation

Co-creation and Business Support

Pilot region: Murcia (Spain) | Period: May-Dec 2018

Challenger

Solver

Users

Supporter

Funder

SMS	Costaisa	Medical Residents	Ticbiomed	INFO
1 SMS Administrative Personnel	1 Product Manager	25 male residents	2 business supporters	2 experts
1 Family Medicine Professional	1 Strategic Business Development	34 female residents		
2 Internal Medicine Professionals	1 Product Owner			
1 SMS Central Services Personnel	1 Senior IT Project Manager			
1 Healthcare Professional from Training Unit	2 IT Developers			
	1 Junior Innovation Project Manager			

Hear the stories!

I thought the applications for the management area were not going to be eligible for co-creation but in inDemand, there is room for everyone.

**María Elena Esteban,
Administrative at SMS**

They have brought knowledge, we have brought the technology, and we have all brought the resources, expertise and desire to create something together.

Inma Roig, Product Manager at Costaisa

The system is a useful, practical way to keep a register and evaluate the resident activities.

Resident

About inDemand

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The inDemand project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No763735.

HECRO → Support for the diagnosis and treatment of chronic wounds

The need

Chronic wounds are skin lesions of more than 4 weeks of evolution that have little or no tendency to healing. Their prevention and treatment are one of the most common care actions within the health activity of nursing professionals in the different care contexts (hospital, primary and social health care). The prevalence of chronic ulcers is high in all countries and settings. Once the ulcer has developed, the correct identification of the type of lesion is a challenge for many professionals, as well as the subsequent choice of the appropriate product for treatment due to the continuous development of new materials and solutions for healing. This generates a wide variability in the response of professionals, which hinders the evolution of wounds by increasing the avoidable costs and treatment time of these injuries.

The solution

A smart digital tool (both desktop and responsive modules) to assist the user with the correct diagnosis of different ulcers and chronic wounds, to guide the user through the process of wound cleaning and treatment and to facilitate the analysis of the wound healing process. The prototype is valid for care at the health centre or at the patient's home.

Impact

The key aspect of the project was the acceptability of the healthcare personnel of the co-created intelligent assistant. Two indicators were used to measure its success - the first measures user average satisfaction and the second the probability of recommendation to third parties (Net Promoter score) - which, in both cases, resulted in a rating of excellent by the users of the assistant.

- Average Satisfaction Score of nurses = 8.87/10
- Net Promoter score →50, excellent (from -100 to 100)

(*) These results come from a trial period between Jan -Mar 2020 with 47 primary care nurses and hospital nurses.

#Chronicwounds

#Nursing

#DigitalTools

Co-creation and Business Support

Pilot region: Murcia (Spain) | June 2019-September 2020

| Funder |
|--|--|---|---|--|
| SMS | Aslogic | Nurses | Ticbiomed | INFO |
| 1 innovation professional
1 IT professional
5 nurse supervisors | 1 CEO
1 Data Scientist
4 software developers
1 designer | 47 primary care and hospital nurses | 2 business supporters | 2 experts |

Hear the stories!

InDemand has given us the opportunity to materialize an idea. Hecro is a tool that helps professionals in the care of their patients with chronic wounds, based on the best available evidence and expert support, facilitating their daily work

**Antonio Martínez Bernal, Nursing
Área Supervisor at SMS**

In addition to the satisfaction of helping patients with chronic wounds, inDemand allowed us to team up with healthcare professionals to address the kind of challenges that we are passionate about.

Pau Folch, Data Scientist at Aslogic

As a user in the Internal Medicine hospitalisation unit, I find this tool very useful in the diagnosis, treatment and follow-up of chronic wounds. It can be used on a daily basis and is essential for a joint and continuous treatment between Primary and Specialised Care.

María José Ruiz, Nurse at SMS

About inDemand

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The inDemand project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No763735.

INTELLIGENT SCREENING →

Using smart application in patient screening for MRI-scans

The need

Currently, the screening of risk information consumes a significant amount of human resources, so that MRI studies can be conducted safely. For example, the medical records in patient record systems are being screened by staff members. Risk assessment includes checking the information systems of several hospitals for possible medical or other foreign bodies and the makes and models of medical foreign bodies. Sometimes records are searched for from the medical records of other hospitals. The patients themselves can also report possible foreign bodies.

Impact

↑30k MRI studies in NOHD yearly
↑500 implants recognized
↓2 full time nurses manually checking contraindications

(* These results come from Regular end-user testing by healthcare professionals during the co-creation at the Oulu University Hospital Testbed

The solution

Neagen's SCS guides medical professionals during the process of planning an MRI study. It gathers information from various integrated information systems, and based on this information, it detects risks and contraindications regarding the planned study. Its guidance is especially important when selecting the correct imaging device prior to scheduling, but can also be relevant after scheduling, in advance of the patient visit and lastly right before imaging. To offer such guidance, the SCS integrates to the radiology production control system, in order to detect and alert about possible contraindications as early as possible in the process.

#HealthAI

#Radiology

#MRI

Co-creation and Business Support

Pilot region: Oulu (Finland) | Period: April 2019- April 2020

Challenger

Oulu University Hospital

4 Nurses
1 MD
1 Quality Manager
2 Innovation experts

Solver

Neagen

1 Senior developer
1 Software developer
1 Product manager

Users

Healthcare Professionals

4 Nurses
1 MD
1 Quality Manager
2 Hospital Physicist

Supporter

BusinessOulu

2 business supporters

Funder

Oulu Region Council

2 experts

Hear the stories!

"We are expecting to speed up the risk screening process and improve patient safety with intelligent screening application."

Kirsi Rannisto, Head Nurse at Oulu University Hospital

The end-user perspective has been crucial in defining the new MRI screening process

Luca Pagani, Product Manager at Neagen

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MENUDO → Mobile digital technologies to treat childhood obesity through education, motivation and adherence

The need

The high prevalence of overweight and obesity has serious consequences for health as it is a major risk factor for diseases such as high blood pressure, heart disease, type 2 diabetes and many cancers (e.g. colorectal, renal and oesophageal). More than 40% of Spanish children between 6 and 9 years old are overweight or obese (see [ALADINO study](#)) with an increasing tendency that could not be reversed despite the interventions made by governments ([NAOS strategy](#)).

The solution

Esporti Family is a mobile application whose objective is to treat childhood obesity which allows sharing information among professionals, patients and families. Through gamification, Esporti Family teaches kids and their families healthy habits and nutrition and encourages them to increase their level of physical activity. Besides, it contributes to their knowledge in health thanks to an AI chatbot that answers to their questions.

Impact

- ↓ **44.4%** decrease in fast food consumption
- ↓ **0.49** reduction in the Body Mass Index z-score
- ↑ **38%** of patients increased hours of weekly exercise
- ↑ **27%** of patients increased sleep hours

(*) These results come from a 2 months trial period

#Gamification

#PatientAdherence

#HealthyHabits

Co-creation and Business Support

Pilot region: Murcia (Spain) | Period: May-Dec 2018

| Funder |
|--|--|---|---|--|
| SMS | Healthy Blue Bits | Patients, relatives | Ticbiomed | INFO |
| 4 paediatricians
1 nutritionist | 1 software engineer
1 medical director | 8 male children
19 female children
40 relatives | 2 business supporters | 2 experts |

Hear the stories!

inDemand was an opportunity to work with other specialists to overcome a complex problem like childhood obesity. We were not expecting changes in the short term but thanks to technology, children have been very motivated and we are really surprised by the results .

**Carmen Vicente,
Paediatrician at SMS**

inDemand helped us to have a better commercial approach and to identify, step by step, how to engage with public organisations.

**Manuel Escobar, CEO & Software
Engineer at Healthy Blue Bits**

Children are self-aware of unhealthy food. They are also aware of the importance of increasing physical activity and that the small changes in habits are what makes you improve.

Mother of an overweight patient

About inDemand

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The inDemand project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No763735.

ONCO → Improve the long-term monitoring of cancer patients

The need

There is a need to accompany patients followed in Oncology and Supportive Care outside the hospital and on discharge by:

- Creating and strengthening the relationship between hospital and self-employed health professionals and optimising multidisciplinary and multi-professional work, by better sharing of information
- Optimising and anticipating the care needs of the patients being monitored, by improving the management of treatment toxicities and symptoms of the disease, thus avoiding visits to the emergency department (as a result of a deterioration in the patient's condition)
- Assistance with maintaining home care for patients.

The project aims to enable the periodic collection and analysis of information on:

- the levels of toxicity of the treatments
- subjective data on the general condition, quality of life and satisfaction of patients.

#e-parcoursOncology

#IntelligentMD

#PatientCarerRelationship

Co-creation and Business Support

Pilot region: Paris (France) | Period: August 2019 – August 2020

| Funder |
|--|--|--|---|--|
| Hôpital Foch | Pandalab | Patients with cancer, from the announcement to the follow-up after remission, and ALL their health care team in the hospital and in the city | Medicen | Choose Paris Region |
| 2 oncologists
1 support care doctor
1 senior health executive
1 health executive
2 nurse coordinators
4 patients
1 IT project manager
1 project Director" | 1 CTO
1 medical advisor
1 general manager
3 developer | 4 patients participated in the co-creation process | 2 business supporters | 1 Project manager |

The solution

Remote monitoring of oncology patients that allows:

- patient care from the announcement of their diagnosis until the follow-up after remission
- connect the city and hospital healthcare professionals with each other
- analysing and issuing monitoring statistics for publication thanks to an intuitive user-validated interface based on secure instant messaging and videoconferencing and an intelligent algorithm created by caregivers and patients for monitoring of supportive care with patient questionnaires and alerts.

Impact

- Improved quality of life and patient satisfaction
- Fewer reports of deteriorating health status as well as fewer visits to the Emergency department
- Improvement of treatment management
- Increased patient survival

(* These results come from regular end-user testing during the project - 12 months

Hear the stories!

This solution will enable us to maintain the relationship with the patients and to work with greater calmness and anticipation. Moreover, in terms of assessment and clinical research, we will have access to very interesting data. Finally, improving the relationship with self-employed health professionals working outside the hospital is a key issue for the years to come.

**Oncology department team at Hôpital Foch
(doctors, health executives and nurse coordinator)**

The co-creation process has enabled us to build a tool that has been thought out and validated by patients and caregivers with a single common objective: to create the best tool that is as useful as possible on a daily basis.

Christelle Masson, CEO at Pandalab

About inDemand

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ORIENTATION BOT FOR HEALTHCARE PROFESSIONALS AND STUDENTS

The need

Guiding and engaging social and healthcare professionals and students in innovation activities demand comprehensive support as well as resources from a hospital innovation management team (IMT). Partial digitalisation of selected training topics of innovation activities completes the support provided by IMT as well as conserves human resources. There is also a need to motivate health care professionals and students to actively familiarise themselves with the topic in question and help to utilize human resources in a more efficient way.

The solution

The interactive Orientation bot complements the activities carried out by Oulu University Hospital in orienting and engaging professionals and students in innovation activities. Bot's operations have been designed during the process that involved the hospital's innovation organization, innovation coordinators and innovation ambassadors in the development work.

Impact

- Increased opportunities for hospital professionals and students to receive guidance in innovation activities.

(*] These results come from Regular end-user testing by healthcare professionals during the co-creation at the Oulu University Hospital Testbed

#Artificialintelligence

#Virtualagent

#Healthinnovations

Co-creation and Business Support

Pilot region: Oulu (Finland) | Period: April 2019- April 2020

| Funder |
|--|--|--|---|--|
| Oulu University Hospital | iSoft.ai | IMTs at Oulu University Hospital | BusinessOulu | Oulu Region Council |
| 7 Innovation Management Team representatives
6 Innovation Ambassadors | 1 software engineer
1 medical director | 13 Innovation Management Team representatives
120+ Innovation Ambassadors
Hospital professionals
Social and healthcare students | 5 business development experts | 2 experts |

Hear the stories!

The Intelligent Orientation bot is expected to serve as an assistive tool in orienting and engaging employees and students in our hospitals' innovation activities.

Pauliina Hyrkäs, Innovation Coordinator of Northern Ostrobothnia Hospital District

Virtual assistants are becoming widely used in many business and public sector organizations. The Orientation Bot shows how new conversational solutions enable innovative working methods. It is also possible to use the same solution easily in other hospital processes

Erkki Lohiniva, CEO at iSoft.ai

About inDemand

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OUTPATIENT CLINIC APPOINTMENT →

Electronic services before and after an outpatient clinic appointment (case: paediatric and adolescent diabetes care pathway)

The need

Type 1 diabetes is more common in Finland than anywhere else. The outpatient clinic for children and young people with diabetes at Oulu University Hospital regularly monitors approximately 470 patients who are under 19 years old. When a child is diagnosed with diabetes and admitted to a hospital ward, diabetes therapy education provided to the patient and his or her family includes insulin administration and injection education, education on blood sugar monitoring, diet guidance, exercise guidance, guidance on social security issues and guidance by a health professional. In addition, blood sugar is monitored, tissue sugar measurements taken, and daily insulin dosage determined. There is a clear need for electronic notes and a communication platform to guide children and young people with diabetes as well as their families through the initial care practices.

The solution

Electronic follow-up forms for monitoring blood sugar levels at hospital wards. The solution is meant for the use of healthcare professionals. The 'MyDiabetes.chat' is an online mobile online handbook and a chat tool that facilitates the communication between diabetes clinics and patients' families.

#Diabetes

#Chronicdiseases

#Healthinnovations

Impact

- For professionals: Technology solution available* for electronic in-hospital blood glucose monitoring. Chat tool for patient and family guidance (real-time and offline communication)
- For patients and families: a comprehensive diabetes handbook 'online-in-your-pocket' and a chat tool for communicating with healthcare professionals

(* These results come from regular end-user testing during the co-creation by healthcare professionals at the Oulu University Hospital Testbed.

Co-creation and Business Support

Pilot region: Oulu (Finland) | Period: May 2018 - December 2018

| Funder |
|--|--|---|---|--|
| Oulu University Hospital | ProWellness Health Solutions | Patients and their relatives | BusinessOulu | Oulu Region Council |
| 6 Nurses
3 MD
2 Innovation Experts | 2 software engineers,
1 project assistant
CEO | 6 female patients
6 male patients
6 female relatives
6 male relatives | 3 business development experts | 2 experts |

Hear the stories!

Co-creation with healthcare professionals is the best way to guarantee that a company stays focused on developing the right solution. In the case of start-ups, business development support is also of great importance.

Mika Sipilä, CEO at ProWellness Health Solutions

Päivi Tossavainen, Medical Director, PhD at Oulu University Hospital was the intrapreneur proposing this challenge

About inDemand

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PAINCARER → Pain Manager for chronic pain patients

The need

There is a need to develop a Finnish language mobile application, which would enable the following actions: self-assessment of pain through different measures, a toolkit of drug-free pain treatment methods, psychoeducation (explaining the causes of pain alleviates the experience of pain), a trigger function for the timing of medicine consumption. There is also a need for enabling communication between the professional and the patient.

The solution

PainCARER is a mobile application for pain self-assessment. This application is a tool for patients suffering from pain to record and assess their pain events. Assessed pain records can be viewed from the application or composed to a report that can be shared with healthcare professionals. It also includes a library of drug-free pain treatment methods and local treatment providers. The application is designed to be user friendly for those interested in tracking and assessing their pain.

Impact

- Better communication between pain patients and health care professionals
- Long term tracking of patient's pain events
- Self-assessing the pain can alleviate symptoms

* These results come from regular end-user testing during the co-creation by healthcare professionals at the Oulu University Hospital Testbed.

#PainSelfAssessment

#ChronicPain

#PatientEmpowerment

Co-creation and Business Support

Pilot region: Oulu (Finland) | April 2019- April 2020

|
Funder |
|--|--|---|---|--|
| Oulu University Hospital | Kipuwex | Oulu University Hospital professionals and Private Expert users | BusinessOulu | Oulu Region Council |
| 4 Nurses
1 Psychologist
2 Innovation Experts | 1 CEO
1 software engineer
1 Product manager
1 Graphic designer
1 Web designer | 4 Nurses
2 Experts by experience | 4 business development experts | 2 experts |

Hear the stories!

Once completed, the mobile solution will provide a novel method for pain self-assessment and interaction with healthcare professionals.

Anne Pietikäinen, Physiotherapist at Oulu University Hospital

Developing a solution for the need is the right way of creating HealthTech products to market. Co-operation with healthcare professionals and pain patients has been guiding our development from day one.

Aleksi Ronkainen, Product Manager at KIPUWEX

PainCAREER is a very important tool in pain event tracking. The body wants to forget the pain events – with a real-time recording of the event by targeting the pain area on a model and assessing the pain or using voice input, that pain can be recorded before forgetting it. Patients can deliver actual information about their pain to health care professionals. The app is easy to use and well instructed!

Pertti Latvala, Chronic pain patient, Expert by experience at Finnish pain association

About inDemand

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RESOURCING PLANNING

Solution supporting resource planning for more efficient implementation of rooms

The need

In the future hospital, the occupancy rate of rooms shall raise in accordance with space requirements. For instance, at outpatient clinics, the number of rooms will be smaller in the future despite the fact, that even now as it is, the hospital does not always have a sufficient number of rooms available. Oulu University Hospital needed a solution supporting resource planning for more efficient implementation of rooms. They wanted to have better visibility on their resources. They needed to be able to plan the usage, find resources and reallocate them easily.

The solution

Our solution proposal was based on an existing cloud-based Delfoi Planner® solution. We realized that the main problem was the lack of transparent resource planning in healthcare. Delfoi Planner healthcare solution enables integrated planning and scheduling for reception times, rooms, doctors, nurses and other staff groups from a secured cloud service (SaaS). Planning is based on the forecasted reception demand, existing rooms and personnel resources and skills. To address an acute need for rooms we developed during the project a new add-on for the existing solution. This add-on was a mobile interface from which it was easy to reserve rooms for a specific need.

Impact

- 84% decrease in planning time
- 34h/day saved on planning of 120 employees
- Concludes into savings of 650.000 € yearly

* These results come from regular end-user testing during the co-creation by healthcare professionals at the Oulu University Hospital Testbed.

#OperationsPlanning

#DigitalHealthcare

#HealthcareResourcePlanning

Co-creation and Business Support

Pilot region: Oulu (Finland) | Period: May 2018 - December 2018

|
Funder |
|--|--|---|---|--|
| Oulu University Hospital | Delfoi | Healthcare professionals from Oulu University Hospital | BusinessOulu | Oulu Region Council |
| 7 nurses
2 MD
1 quality manager
2 secretaries
2 innovation experts
1 IT expert | 1 CEO
1 VP of Operations
1 Project manager
2 software engineers
1 healthcare consultant | 7 nurses
2 MD
2 secretaries | 2 business supporters | 2 experts |

Hear the stories!

InDemand was an eye-opening project for us. Before the project we had a need to find vacant rooms. During the project, we realized that good operations planning is the key to well working and efficient hospital.

Vesa, Kiljunen, Head nurse at Oulu University Hospital

When the need for a solution has been presented, challenge it, discuss with the customer and find the root cause of the problem by working together as a team. This is how the idea will turn into a great solution to the problem.

Tomi, Nurmi, Project Manager at Delfoi

Operations planning & control is a complex system in health-care. It involves several different ICT-systems, which are not connected through integration. Delfoi demonstrated for us a software, which can digitalize the planning and connect these different systems together through integrations. When implemented properly, this can have a large impact on the efficiency of the hospital.

Jukka Rantanen, ICT-coordinator at Oulu University Hospital

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RESPIRATORY RATE MONITOR

Machine vision in respiratory rate monitoring

The need

When monitoring patients, breathing is one of the most important vital functions to pay attention to. An abnormal respiratory rate can be a predictor of serious adverse outcomes, such as sepsis among patients with infections, and is a key component in Emergency triage. However, peer-reviewed studies have consistently highlighted serious gaps in recording respiratory rates: most recently only 36% of measurements were considered accurate (Journal of Hospital Medicine, Keshvani et al 2019). Improvement in monitoring with a new measuring instrument would help healthcare professionals in their daily work and improve the quality of care in speciality and primary healthcare.

Impact

- Respiratory rate information is available in triage situations.
- Real world usage identified improvements, including better handling of patient movement.
- 4 in 5 nurses surveyed found the solution very easy or easy to use.

* Pilot study at the Emergency Department of Oulu University Hospital

The solution

The NE Device SW vital signs monitor **Vitacam™** uses computer vision and a regular digital camera to remotely measure respiratory rate. The software application counts the chest movements of a patient, observing multiple landmarks on the chest simultaneously to obtain a more reliable measurement. Neither expensive specialized equipment nor physical contact with a patient is needed. During emergency triage assessment, the software supports clinical decision-making by providing continuous, real-time measurements. As much of the process is automated, the clinician is able to focus on other tasks while still gaining valuable intel on a patient's condition. By providing nurses with additional clinical data, our goal to improve patient safety. **Vitacam™** can also be adapted to a smartphone and cloud-based solution for remote monitoring.

#Contactless

#Customizable

#ClinicalSafety

Co-creation and Business Support

Pilot region: Oulu (Finland) | Period: April 2019- April 2020

Challenger	Solver	Users	Supporter	Funder
Oulu University Hospital	NE Device SW	Nurses	BusinessOulu	Oulu Region Council
3 Nurses 1 MD 2 Project Designers 2 Innovation Experts	3 software engineers 1 QA specialist	30+ Nurses	5 business development experts	2 experts

Hear the stories!

The solution makes it possible to measure the respiratory rate from unmonitored patients. It is great to see how an idea turns into reality.

Marja Ylilehto, Nurse and Project Designer at Oulu University Hospital

Co-developing a product with healthcare professionals has been truly a joy. The seamless dialogue enabled us to prune the product fully for the actual use-case, knowing what can be beneficial. With the rising healthcare needs and newly invented technological possibilities, this way of working is hopefully here to stay.

Miikka Kirveskoski, Chief Technology Officer at NE DEVICE SW

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SAFEFOCH → Remote monitoring of real-life patient data to anticipate the occurrence of complications in health status

The need

At Foch Hospital, 936 patients have benefited from kidney transplants and are regularly monitored. 90 new patients are transplanted every year. Between the consultations, doctors lack information regarding the patients and have to look in multiple (paper) files. In parallel, patients can be stressed and unsure about their prescriptions or wonder what their biological results mean.

The solution

NephroWise is a follow-up and support solution for patients with kidney transplants and care teams. NephroWise aims to optimize medical time and empower medical decision making using AI technology. The solution captures medical data (vital signs, care pathway, biology results...), executes rules and alerts the care team in a user-friendly web portal. It also includes AI-driven predictive algorithms to help nephrologists identifying patients at high risk of severe outcomes. The patient support web app allows to gather PROs and offer a unique digital health education experience.

Impact

- More than 60 patients telemonitored 10 months after the launch and 10 HCPs involved
- High satisfaction rate from the early adopters and users (healthcare professional and patients)

(*) These results come from a 6 months trial period

#DigitalHealth

#UserFriendly

#Transplant

Co-creation and Business Support

Pilot region: Paris (France) | Period: September 2018 – March 2019

| Funder |
|---|--|---|---|--|
| Hôpital Foch & Resah | Sêmeia | Healthcare professional and patients after kidney transplant | Medicen | Choose Paris Region |
| 1 project director
1 project manager
2 nephrologists
1 quality director
1 information systems director
1 nurse coordinator
2 nurses | 2 project managers
3 developers | 3 nephrologists
1 nurse
6 patients | 2 business supporters | 1 project manager |

Hear the stories!

In a single tool, we gather all the information required to assess efficiently the condition of our patients and take care of them. Working directly with patients was very insightful to better design the tool to better respond to their needs also. This tool made it possible to monitor patients remotely during the coronavirus epidemic.

Dr. Albane BRODIN-SARTORIUS,
Nephrologist at Hopital Fôch

The co-creation with patients and HCPs led us to design a user-centric solution that ensures a high tool adoption and satisfaction

Delphine Leseul, Project Manager at Sêmeia

I am very happy with using Sêmeia for several reasons. Apart from having a general view of our various personal data (examinations, blood pressure, weight, etc.), this allows a much faster patient / doctor relationship. The fact of being contacted and oriented on the exams (or others) to do as soon as something goes wrong has a real interest, as well as a very reassuring side. For me, the real plus is being able to warn the doctor when I feel I have a problem. Prompt feedback from the doctor avoids wasting time, which can be very important in certain situations.

Patient

About inDemand

inDemand boosts digital health solutions proposed and co-created with healthcare professionals

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Contact the developers:
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The inDemand project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No763735.

SENSE4HEALTH → Remote-controlled mobile solution for hospital clients (case: children’s asthma examination)

The need

At present, children’s asthma tests start with two appointments. The first appointment is with a nurse. It contains a lot of important guidance to promote successful diagnostic tests, including guidance on blowing into the PEF meter, two-week PEF monitoring and instruction on taking inhaled medication. The second appointment is related to pulmonary function tests and nurse’s and doctor’s surgery. Some clients could skip the first appointment with the nurse if they had access to high-quality materials and the asthma tests could be carried out in one visit without compromising the reliability of diagnostic tests. The application is needed for the purpose of submitting guidance material in various domestic and international units and organisations.

The solution

The Astmatti app encourages its user to learn basic skills to perform asthma examination. Astmatti guidance material includes a video, which provides instruction on peak expiratory flow measurement and taking medication in a proper way via dry-powder inhalers. The Astmatti app can visualize health organizations’ own guidance material in a mobile app. Astmatti app guidance can be individualized, which makes it easier for the patient to follow the examination trail according to health organizations protocol. For example, the patient can be reminded to pause the asthma medication in the correct timely manner before spirometry examinations in the outpatient department.

Potential Impact

- Astmatti-app helps children and young people to prepare for asthma tests at home
- Better performance in PEF measurement
- Better performance in taking dry powder inhaled medication

* These results come from regular end-user testing during the co-creation by healthcare professionals at the Oulu University Hospital Testbed.

#Astmatti

#HealthInnovations

#ChildrenAsthmarcePlanning

Co-creation and Business Support

Pilot region: Oulu (Finland) | Period: May 2018 - December 2018

Challenger	Solver	Users	Supporter	Funder
Oulu University Hospital	Sense 4Health	Patients, relatives	BusinessOulu	Oulu Region Council
3 Nurses 1 Head Nurse 1 MD 2 Innovation Experts	1 software engineer 1 medical director	1 patient 2 relatives	3 business development experts	2 experts

Hear the stories!

As a public health organization, we were able to carry out an interesting co-creation process with Sense4Health. As a result, we got the Astmatti-app for children and young people to prepare for asthma tests.

Marjo Lepistö, Deputy Head Nurse at Oulu University Hospital

Astmatti supports self-management and potentially improves consequently asthma control.

Miika Arvonen, Specialist in Pediatrics, PhD, Sense4Health

Astmatti helped me to perform PEF-monitoring properly.

Patient: Ilkka 10 year old, male

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better health

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